

Data Management Plan Information

La Chouffe DMP

This DMP has been created for managing data representative of the Open Publishing domain. Starting from our research questions related to scientometric studies, we aim at evaluating the management at the state-of-the-art of data linked to articles (references) and to have an idea of how much the aggregators communicate with each other in terms of information sharing.

Our research involves the articles from Open Access journals in DOAJ and their data on Crossref. The produced datasets will be created combining the manipulation of both datasets retrieved from the above mentioned sources.

Funder

None

Grant

none

Organisations

Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna

Researchers

Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426), Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053), Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)

Datasets

Title: DOAJ data

Template: Horizon 2020

This dataset gathers all the DOIs of journals retrieved from DOAJ. The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ, <https://doaj.org/>) is an independent index containing more than 17,500 peer-reviewed, open access journals covering all areas of science, technology, medicine, social sciences, arts and humanities

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To combine with other data
- This data will be combined with Crossref data

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

• reference or canonical (e.g., static, peer-reviewed data sets, likely published or curated, such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

- Data will be gathered from dumps made available by DOAJ or from their API

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

- Text files, Numerical
- Files will contain both numerical and textual information about each journal

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Secondary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

GB (gigabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers, Research communities, Decision makers, Education, Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes

- Dublin Core

- We re keeping it general for now

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- No

- We will take this possibility into consideration as the project progresses

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

- No

- Only if needed

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

- Yes

- Yes, we will use DOIs

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

- Linked Open Data

- OpenAIRE

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

- Yes

- 8-bit ASCII Text

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes

- .json;

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?
Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?
Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?
No

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?
Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- GitHub

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?
insecure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?
No

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?
no auxiliary data

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?
Yes

3.1.3.2 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?
Maybe

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?
end of project

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?
• Yes

- In the future they will be added

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes
Data conform to format specification, Consistency verified with data models and standards

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

Yes

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

- No

- We do not have a designed person for now, but will be decided

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.

- Giulia Venditti (orcid:0000-0001-7696-7574)

- updates

b.

- Davide Brembilla (orcid:0000-0002-9481-5053)

- updates

c.

- Chiara Catizone (orcid:0000-0003-2445-2426)

- updates

4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Institutional archive, Other, Personal Archive

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

No

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

Yes

7.1.2 Please provide links to documentation on these other procedures

<https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004525>

Title: La Software

Template: Horizon 2020

Crossref dois data also present in DOAJ

Dataset Description

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

- To obtain information, To share information, To develop a product
 - This is a software developed to perform scientometric analyses on our DOAJ and Crossref data. It will be divided in components aimed at managing different stages of data manipulation and perform different measures on this data.

It will be developed using python programming language.

1.1.2 What are the types of the described generated/collected data?

- experimental (e.g., gene sequencing data), simulation (e.g., climate modeling data)
 - These are our two first proposals of generated data. This section will be reviewed.

1.1.3 What are the formats of the described generated/collected data?

Software

1.1.4 What is the origin of the described data?

Primary data

1.1.5 What is the expected size of the described data?

MB (megabyte)

1.1.6 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Researchers, Research communities, Industry

2.1 Reused Data

2.1.1 Are you re-using the described data and how?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 Will you use metadata to describe the data?

- Yes

- Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

3.1.1.2 Please provide URL/Location describing the used metadata schema

- <https://vocab.org/frbr/core>

- FRBR

3.1.1.3 Will your metadata use standardised vocabularies?

- No
 - To be revised

3.1.1.5 Will you make the metadata available free-of-charge?

No

3.1.1.6 Will your metadata be harvestable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 Will you use naming conventions for your data?

No

3.1.1.9 Will you provide clear version numbers for your data?

Yes

3.1.1.10 Will you provide persistent identifiers for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.11 Persistent identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.12 Will you provide searchable metadata for the described data?

Yes

3.1.1.13 What services will you use to provide searchable metadata?

- Linked Open Data
- OpenAIRE

3.1.1.15 Will you use standardised formats for the described data?

- Yes
- 8-bit ASCII Text

3.1.1.18 Are the file formats you will use open?

- Yes
 - .py

3.1.1.20 Do supported open-source tools exist for accessing the data?

Yes

3.1.1.22 Will you provide metadata describing the quality of the data?

Yes

3.1.2 Making data openly accessible

3.1.2.1 Are there ethical or legal issues that can impact sharing the described data?

- Yes
 - Authorship of the code

3.1.2.2 Will the described data be openly accessible?

Yes

3.1.2.3 How will the data be made available?

- Other
- GitHub

3.1.2.5 Is the storage sufficiently secure for the data and does the storage provide backup and recovery procedures?

insecure with backup and recovery

3.1.2.6 Are there any methods or tools required to access the described data?

No

3.1.2.9 Will you also make auxiliary data that may be of interest to researchers available?

at end of project

3.1.3 Making data interoperable

3.1.3.1 Will you use a controlled vocabulary for the described data?

Yes

3.1.4 Increase data reuse

3.1.4.1 When do you plan to make the described data available for reuse?

end of project

3.1.4.5 Do you have documented procedures for quality assurance of the described data?

- Yes
 - testing

3.1.4.7 Describe the data quality assurance processes

Use of tools for automatic checks

3.1.4.8 Will you provide any support for data reuse?

- Yes
 - Data dumps, code workflow (?)

3.1.4.9 How long do you intend to support data reuse?

Up to 5 years

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 How will the cost of making the described data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable be covered?

- Use of institution infrastructure, Other
- web platform

4.1.2 Will you identify a data manager to manage the described data? If not who will be responsible for the management of the data?

Yes

4.1.3 Identify the people or roles that will be responsible for the management of the described data

a.

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- updates

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4.1.4 How do you intend to ensure data reuse after your project finishes?

Personal Archive

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 Where do you plan to keep the described data?

Kept on secure, managed storage for limited time

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

- Yes
- authorship

6.1.2 Are the described data sensitive?

No

6.1.3 Are the described data personal?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

Title: Crossref data
Template: Horizon 2020

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<https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004525>